

СЎЗ САНЪАТИ ХАЛҚАРО ЖУРНАЛИ

7 ЖИЛД, 2 СОН

МЕЖДУНАРОДНЫЙ ЖУРНАЛ ИСКУССТВО СЛОВА

ТОМ 7, НОМЕР 2

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF WORD ART

VOLUME 7, ISSUE 2

СЎЗ САНЪАТИ ХАЛҚАРО ЖУРНАЛИ

МЕЖДУНАРОДНЫЙ ЖУРНАЛ ИСКУССТВО СЛОВА | INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF WORD ART

№2 (2024) DOI <http://dx.doi.org/10.26739/2181-9297-2024-2>

Бош муҳаррир:
Тўхтасинов Илҳом
п.ф.д., профессор (Ўзбекистон)

Бош муҳаррир ўринбосари:

Главный редактор:
Тухтасинов Илхом
д.п.н., профессор (Узбекистан)

Заместитель главного редактора:

Editor in Chief:
Tuhtasinov Ilhom
DSc. Professor (Uzbekistan)

Deputy Chief Editor

ТАҲРИРИЙ МАСЛАҲАТ КЕНГАШИ

Назаров Бахтиёр
академик. (Ўзбекистон)

Якуб Умарўғли
ф.ф.д., профессор (Туркия)

Алмаз Улви Биннатова
ф.ф.д., профессор (Озарбайжон)

Бокиева Гуландом
ф.ф.д., профессор (Ўзбекистон)

Миннуллин Ким
ф.ф.д., профессор (Татаристон)

Махмудов Низомиддин
ф.ф.д., профессор (Ўзбекистон)

Керимов Исмаил
ф.ф.д., профессор (Россия)

Жўраев Маматкул
ф.ф.д., профессор (Ўзбекистон)

Куренов Рахиммаед
к.ф.н. (Туркменистон)

Кристофер Жеймс Форт
Мичиган университети (АҚШ)

Умархўжаев Мухтор
ф.ф.д., профессор (Ўзбекистон)

Мирзаев Ибодулло
ф.ф.д., профессор (Ўзбекистон)

Болтабоев Ҳамидулла
ф.ф.д., профессор (Ўзбекистон)

Дўстмухаммедов Хуршид
ф.ф.д., профессор (Ўзбекистон)

Лиходзиевский А.С.
ф.ф.д., профессор (Ўзбекистон)

Сиддикова Ирода
ф.ф.д., профессор (Ўзбекистон)

Шиукашвили Тамар
ф.ф.д. (Грузия)

Туробов Бекпулат
масбул котиб, PhD, доцент
(Ўзбекистон)

РЕДАКЦИОННЫЙ СОВЕТ

Назаров Бахтиёр
академик. (Узбекистан)

Якуб Умар оглы
д.ф.н., профессор (Туркия)

Алмаз Улви Биннатова
д.ф.н., профессор (Азербайджан)

Бакиева Гуландом
д.ф.н., профессор (Узбекистан)

Миннуллин Ким
д.ф.н., профессор (Татарстан)

Махмудов Низомиддин
д.ф.н., профессор (Узбекистан)

Керимов Исмаил
д.ф.н., профессор (Россия)

Джураев Маматкул
д.ф.н., профессор (Узбекистан)

Куренов Рахыммаед
к.ф.н. (Туркменистан)

Кристофер Жеймс Форт
Университет Мичигана (США)

Умархаджаев Мухтар
д.ф.н., профессор (Узбекистан)

Мирзаев Ибодулло
д.ф.н., профессор (Узбекистан)

Балтабоев Ҳамидулла
д.ф.н., профессор (Узбекистан)

Дустмухаммедов Хуршид
д.ф.н., профессор (Узбекистан)

Лиходзиевский А.С.
д.ф.н., профессор (Узбекистан)

Сиддикова Ирода
д.ф.н., профессор (Узбекистан)

Шиукашвили Тамар
д.ф.н. (Грузия)

Туробов Бекпулат
отв. секретарь, PhD, доцент
(Узбекистан)

EDITORIAL BOARD

Bakhtiyor Nazarov
academician. (Uzbekistan)

Yakub Umarogli
Doc. of philol. scien., prof. (Turkey)

Almaz Ulvi Binnatova
Doc. of philol. scien., prof. (Azerbaijan)

Bakieva Gulandom
Doc. of philol. scien., prof. (Uzbekistan)

Minnulin Kim
Doc. of philol. scien., prof. (Tatarstan)

Mahmudov Nizomiddin
Doc. of philol. scien., prof. (Uzbekistan)

Kerimov Ismail
Doc. of philol. scien., prof. (Russia)

Juraev Mamatkul
Doc. of philol. scien., prof. (Uzbekistan)

Kurenov Rakhimmamed
Ph.D. Ass. Prof. (Turkmenistan)

Christopher James Fort
University of Michigan (USA)

Umarkhodjaev Mukhtar
Doc. of philol. scien., prof. (Uzbekistan)

Mirzaev Ibodulla
Doc. of philol. scien., prof. (Uzbekistan)

Boltaboev Hamidulla
Doc. of philol. scien., prof. (Uzbekistan)

Dustmuhammedov Khurshid
Doc. of philol. scien., prof. (Uzbekistan)

Lixodzievsky A.S.
Doc. of philol. scien., prof. (Uzbekistan)

Siddiqova Iroda
Doc. of philol. scien., prof. (Uzbekistan)

Shiukashvili Tamar
Doc. of philol. scien. (Georgia)

Turobov Bekpulat
PhD Ass. prof. Senior Secretary
(Uzbekistan)

PageMaker | Верстка | Саҳифаловчи: Хуршид Мирзахмедов

Контакт редакций журналов. www.tadqiqot.uz
ООО Tadqiqot город Ташкент,
улица Амира Темура пр.1, дом-2.
Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; E-mail: info@tadqiqot.uz
Тел: (+998-94) 404-0000

Editorial staff of the journals of www.tadqiqot.uz
Tadqiqot LLC The city of Tashkent,
Amir Temur Street pr.1, House 2.
Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; E-mail: info@tadqiqot.uz
Phone: (+998-94) 404-0000

1. Cho'liyevich Ne'matilla Oripov HAYKALTAROSHLIK SAN'ATIDA QADRIYATLAR IFODASINI IDROK ETILISHI.....	5
2. Khurshida Narkhodjayeva, J. Ismatova TERMINOLOGICAL LEXICOGRAPHY IS A REFLECTION OF THE DEMAND OF THE TIME AND THE DEVELOPMENT OF LINGUISTICS.....	9
3. Saliyeva Nigora Ikromovna, Djurayev Dilshod Mamadiyarovich O'ZBEK TALABALARINING HSK 5-DARAJASI 写作“YOZUV” BO'LIMINI TOPSHIRISHDA YO'L QO'YGAN LEKSIK XATOLARI TAHLILI.....	13
4. Mamajonov Muhammadjon Yusbjonovich MULOQOT BOSQICHLARINING PSIXOLINGVISTIK TALQINI.....	22
5. Achilova Nurxon Normammedovna QADIMGI XITOIY MIFOLOGIYASIDA AJDARHOLAR VA ULARNING TURLARI.....	28
6. Mirzayeva Mahliyo G'ayrat qizi U. SHEKSPIR “OTELLO” VA M. SHAYXZODA “MIRZO ULUG'BEK” ASARLARIDA BOSH QAHRAMONLAR SHAXSIYATI VA EMOTSIONAL HOLATINING QIYOSIY TAHLILI.....	33
7. Mohinur Baratboyevna Nizomova NUTQIY MULOQOTDA PEDAGOGIKAGA OID TERMINLAR ORQALI YUZAGA KELADIGAN “PEDAGOGIK TIL KONTAKTI” TUSHUNCHASI VA UNING TASNIFI (INGLIZ VA O'ZBEK TILLARI MISOLIDA).....	38
8. Maftuna Do'smurod qizi Elmirzayeva INGLIZ VA O'ZBEK TILLARDAGI IJTIMOIIY HIMOYA TERMINLARNING STRUKTUR TAHLILI.....	44
9. Шамситдинова Зебо Фазлитдиновна ВЫРАЖЕНИЕ В КИТАЙСКОМ ЯЗЫКЕ ФОРМЫ ДАВНОПРОШЕДШЕГО ВРЕМЕНИ, ОБРАЗОВАННОГО В СОВРЕМЕННОМ УЗБЕКСКОМ ЯЗЫКЕ ПРИ ПОМОЩИ АФФИКСА ПРИЧАСТИЯ -GAN.....	50
10. Озодахон Мусаева АБДУРАХИМ ПРАТОВ ШЕЪРИЯТИНИНГ ЛИНГВОДИДАКТИК ТАМОЙИЛЛАРИ.....	58
11. Минхожиддин Хожиматов, АБДУРАУФ ФИТРАТ ШЕЪРИЯТИДА МИЛЛИЙ ЎЗЛИК ВА ҚАЛЬ ИНҚИЛОБИ.....	67
12. Mirxodjaeva Gulrux Miralieva INGLIZ TILINI O'RGANISHDA MUXANDISLIK YO'NALISHI TALABALARI UCHUN SAMARALI ESLAB QOLISH USULLARI.....	77
13. Saidova Rayhon Bekmurodovna ZAMONAVIIY ADABIYOTDA SHE'R VA SHOIRLIK MASALASINING BADIY-ESTETIK TALQINI.....	83
14. Nazarova Dildora Ithomovna ZAMONAVIIY SHE'RIYATDA VAZNLAR RANG-BARANGLIGI.....	89
15. Farkhodova Shahzoda Umidkizi THE PRINCIPLE OF POLITENESS IN SPEECH ADAPTATION.....	96
16. Taxmina Yunusovna Mukaramkhodjayeva SEMANTIC RELATIONSHIPS OF PHRASEOLOGICAL UNITS IN ENGLISH: POLYSEMY AND HOMONYMY.....	102
17. Isoqova Feruza Shamsiddin qizi INGLIZ TILIDA SIYOSIY DISKURSNING LINGVISTIK XUSUSIYATLARI.....	106
18. J.Ro'ziyev BO'LAJAK TASVIRIIY SAN'AT O'QITUVCHILARINING KASBIY KOMPETENSIYASINI SHAKLLANTIRISHDA KOMPOZITSIYANING O'RNI VA AHAMIYATI.....	111

19. Islomova Madina Asqarovna NEMIS MATBUOT MATNLARIDA KOMIZMNING TURLARINING QO'LLANILISHI.....	114
20. Hamroyeva Maftuna Rasulovna LAQABLARNING ANTROPONIMIK BIRLIK SIFATIDA LISONIY TIZIMDAGI O'RNI VA SOTSIOPRAGMATIK XUSUSIYATLARI.....	122
21. Dushanova Nargiza Mamatkulovna THE DEVELOPMENT OF HIGHER-ORDER COGNITIVE COMPETENCIES THROUGH THE PHENOMENON- BASED LEARNING APPROACH.....	127
22. Mardanova Guljahon Furqatkizi EXPRESSION OF THE CONCEPT OF "WEALTH" IN PAREMIOLOGICAL UNITS OF UZBEK LANGUAGE..	135
23. Mardonova Sitara Mardonovna SEMANTIC DEVELOPMENT OF THE VERBS "FEORRIAN, FYRSIAN, FEORSIAN" AND VERBS OF DIRECTION, WHICH ARE INCLUDED IN 4 CATEGORIES OF OLD ENGLISH.....	141
24. Mamajonov Muhammadjon Yusubjonovich MULOQOT BOSQICHLARINING PSIXOLINGVISTIK TALQINI.....	149
25. Бўронов Назим ФЕЙК ВА ДЕЗИНФОРМАЦИЯГА ҚАРШИ КУРАШИШДА МЕДИАСАВОДХОНЛИКНИНГ ВАЗИФАЛАРИ.....	155
26. Narzullaeva Diyora Zayniddin kizi STRUCTURAL ANALYSIS OF POTTERY TERMINOLOGY IN DIFFERENT LANGUAGE SYSTEMS.....	161
27. Islombek Raxmonberdiyev Ilxom o'gli SAMYUEL F. HANTINGTON SIVILIZATSIYALAR TO'QNASHUVI PARADIGMASI IJTIMOY-FALSAFIY TAHLILI.....	167
28. Bobonazarova Gulxayo Habibulla qizi KOGNITIV TILSHUNOSLIKNING KELIB CHIQISHI VA UNGA HISSA QO'SHGAN TILSHUNOSLAR.....	176
29. Eshimova Sharofat Kenjaboyevna, Davlatova Komila Abdusattorovna KOREYS TILIDAGI METAFORA HODISASIDA KO'CHMA MA'NOLI SO'ZLAR XUSUSIDA.....	181
30. Kuvondikova Gavhar Isomiddinovna TALABALAR NUTQINING TA'LIMIY KORPUSINI YARATISHNING NAZARIY MASALALARI.....	189
31. Burxonov Utkir Farxod o'g'li ISPAN TILIDAGI ARABIZMLARNING FONETIK TASNIFI.....	197
32. Muxamedjanova Sh.B. XITOIY TILIDA INTERNET LINGVISTIKASI XUSUSIYATLARI.....	201

Фойдаланилган адабиётлар рўйхати

1. Муратова Н., Тошпулатова Н., Алимова Г. Fake news: медиада дезинформация [Матн]: қўлланма /.. – Ташкент: “Innovatsion rivojlanish nashriyot-matbaa uyi”, 2020. – Б.12.
2. Kubey, R. (1998). Obstacles to the Development of Media Education in the United States. *Journal of Communication* (Winter), pp.58-69.
3. Павликова М.М. Парадоксы информационного общества. Вестник МГУ, серия 10. Журналистика.- №1. 2008 Б. 35.
4. Маматова Я.М., Сулайманова С.Н. Ўзбекистон медиатаълим тараққиёти йўлида. Ўқув қўлланма. – Т.: Extremum-press, 2015. Б 23.
5. Медиа саводхонлик бўйича халқаро конференцияда МАСни тарғиб қилишнинг миллий стратегиялари таклиф қилинди | Янги репортер (newreporter.org).
6. Лебедева Е.Г. Фейковые новости как инструмент манипулятивного воздействия в медиасреде // *Universum: филология и искусствоведение :электрон. научн. журн.* 2021. 3(81). URL: <https://7universum.com/ru/philology/archive/item/>
7. Дўстмухаммад Х. Ахборот мўъжиза, жозиба, фалсафа, Т.: “Янги аср авлоди” 2013.Б. 317, Б. 44
8. Исмаилова К.Ф. Медиаобразование в Узбекистане: тенденции, проблемы, перспективы // *Ўзбекистонда хорижий тиллар*, 2016. – № 6.
9. Раҳимова Ш. Ёшларда ахборот алмашинуви маданиятини ривожлантириш истиқболлари // *Infolib*, 2020. – № 1.\
10. Смирнов А. “Глубокие фейки”: сущность и оценка потенциального влияния на национальную безопасность // *Свободная мысль*, 2019. – № 5. – С. 70; Суходолов А.П. Феномен “фейковых новостей” в современном медиaprостранстве / *Евроазиатское сотрудничество, гуманитарные аспекты: материалы Международной конф.* – Иркутск: Изд-во Байкальского гос. ун-та, 2017. – С.

ISSN: 2181-9297

www.tadqiqot.uz

Narzullaeva Diyora Zayniddin kizi.
PhD Student of Samarkand State
Institute of Foreign Languages

STRUCTURAL ANALYSIS OF POTTERY TERMINOLOGY IN DIFFERENT LANGUAGE SYSTEMS

 <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13236077>

ABSTRACT

The article compares the lexico-grammatical features of pottery terminology of two different systematic languages. Also, special attention is paid to the structural analysis of pottery terms. In both languages, simple terms, that is, nouns, are a group of terms in the vocabulary of a comparative language compared to other parts of speech. The issue is highlighted that the vocabulary and terminology of pottery are a separate part of the lexical structure of each language and its inextricable connection with many branches of production, representatives of the people and human thinking.

Key words: pottery terms, grammatical analysis, structural analysis, terminology, words and terms.

Narzullayeva Diyora Zayniddin qizi
Samarqand davlat chet tillar
instituti tayanch doktoranti

TURLI TILLAR TIZIMIDA KULOLCHILIK TERMINOLOGIYASINING STRUKTURAVIY TAHLILI

ANNOTATSIYA

Mazkur maqolada ikki turli tizimli tillarida kulolchilik terminologiyasining leksik-grammatik xususiyatlari qiyosiy tahlil qilingan. Shuningdek, kulolchilik atamalarining strukturaviy tahliliga alohida e'tibor qaratilgan. Har ikki tilda ham sodda atamalar ya'ni ot atamalar boshqa gap bo'laklariga nisbatan qiyosiy tilning lug'aviy tarkibidagi atamalar guruhini ifodalaganligi masalalari yoritib berilgan. Kulolchilik lug'ati va terminologiyasi har bir tilning leksik tarkibining alohida qismi ekanligi hamda u ishlab chiqarishning ko'plab tarmoqlari, xalq vakili va inson tafakkuri bilan uzviy bog'liqligi masalalari yoritib berilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: kulolchilik terminlari, grammatik tahlil, strukturaviy tahlil, terminologiya, so'z va atamalar.

Нарзуллаева Диёра Зайниддин кизи
Докторант Самаркандского государственного
института иностранных языков

СТРУКТУРНЫЙ АНАЛИЗ ГОНЧАРНОЙ ТЕРМИНОЛОГИИ В РАЗНЫХ ЯЗЫКОВЫХ СИСТЕМАХ

АННОТАЦИЯ

В статье сравниваются лексико-грамматические особенности гончарной терминологии двух разных систематических языков. Также особое внимание уделяется структурному анализу гончарных терминов. В обоих языках простые термины, то есть существительные, представляют собой группу терминов в словаре сравнительного языка по сравнению с другими частями речи. Освещается вопрос о том, что лексика и терминология гончарного дела являются отдельной частью лексического строя каждого языка и его неразрывной связи со многими отраслями производства, представителями народа и человеческого мышления.

Ключевые слова: гончарные термины, грамматический анализ, структурный анализ, терминология, слова и термины.

Introduction

Pottery vocabulary and terminology is a separate part of the lexical structure of each language. It is inextricably linked with many branches of production, representative of the people and human thinking. The words and terms of this lexical layer, known as pottery terminology in the language system, are reflected in the works of historians and ethnographers who dedicated their works to this or that specific craft. Currently, terminology is in the focus of world linguistics along with various topics. It is during this period that one of the most difficult tasks is to find a "terminology" that has acquired a wider meaning and is studied in depth in the science of modern linguistics. Terminology is one of the current directions of modern linguistic research. Currently, the growth of the issue of terminology, on the one hand, is considered to be due to the increase of new concepts due to the dynamic development of science, and on the other hand, it is explained as a phenomenon related to the insufficient study of issues such as the process of formation, development and function of terms. Terminology is a very large part of the vocabulary of every language. It's very fast development is also remarkable, because it allows to create new words. The terminology of a language consists of a system of many terms. A word or phrase in a special field of knowledge, industry or culture is called a term. The meaning of a word expressed by the term is interpreted by explaining it in a thematic literature. Z. Harris and I.F. Frizyslar wrote that the word expression can be considered a linguistic term. They are proponents of descriptive linguistics and define utterance as follows: "An utterance is any human speech that may be expressed before or after a silence." Each department or school of science develops a special terminology adapted to its nature and methods. Such special terminology is an important part of scientific research and is of great importance.

Because it makes a great contribution to development. The terminology of this field is constantly expanding as new technical tools have penetrated more and more. One of such fields is the field of polygraphy and authorship, which is engaged in today's book production. If we pay attention to the development of this field, the entry of technical means into this field mainly coincides with the beginning of the twentieth century. But its most advanced period is today. Today's modern polygraphy-publishing network has become one of the leading industries in which technical tools are used that integrate the processes of preparation of documents and reproduction of their copies, turning them into books. As a result, many new concepts and new scientific and technical terms are entering the terminology of this field. However, B. N. Golovin suggests using the terms "terminology" and "terminological system" as synonyms denoting a set of terms related to each other at the conceptual, lexical-semantic, word-formation, and grammatical levels in the fields of professional activity. Other authors, on the contrary, argue that it is necessary to distinguish between the concepts of "terminology" and "terminological system", that is, under the concept of "terminology" is a set of terms that spontaneously accumulates, and "terminological system" is a certain specialized area of human knowledge or activity. they propose to understand a set of organized terms that adequately represent the system of concepts describing the field. In all the works devoted to terminology, the units that represent specific concepts of one or another field, have a definition and mainly perform a nominative function are considered to be terms. A.Reformatsky defines the term and concludes that "... terms are special words." A.V. Kalinin calls the words used in certain disciplines and professions "special lexicon" and divides it into two groups.

1. The special lexicon includes, first of all, terms.
2. In addition to terms, the special lexicon also includes professionalisms. He continued his opinion and said, "The difference between the term and professionalism is that the term is the expression, the name of a concept that is official, accepted and legalized in a certain science, industry, agriculture, technology, and professionalism. a profession, a specialty, is often a semi-official word that is widespread in everyday language and does not have a strict, scientific description of the concept. It is known that the level of development and improvement of each field of science is inextricably linked with such signs as the level of development and regulation of the terminology of this field. Because if the term used in scientific literature or its form of expression is not clear and unambiguous, negative situations such as confusion and ambiguity will certainly remain. Therefore, as noted by V. P. Danilenko, the progress indicator of each science or field is also determined by the fact that the terminology of this field has "strict scientific terminology". V. P. Danilenko here considers the concept of "strict scientific terminology" to be the combination of any field terminology with the development of this field of science, the coherence of the field terminology in expressing the concepts related to the same field, and the compatibility of the created and used terminology with the specific scientific language.

It should be noted that pottery is one of the oldest crafts of the Tajik and British peoples, and experts in this field face many problems in understanding its vocabulary to this day, because the terms of this field have not been carefully studied. One of the important aspects of the study and comparison of this type of terms is that until today the masters of the pottery industry used its Russian forms and had to interpret them in their native languages. The main reason for this phenomenon is the influence of the Russian language on the Tajik language during the Soviet period, as a result of which many words entered the lexical structure of the Tajik language, as well as insufficient attention to the ceramic terminology of experts. The words and terms of pottery, which belong to one of the important layers of the scientific vocabulary of the Tajik and English languages, have a rich and ancient historical basis, because since ancient times, man has taken his place in society and ensured its existence with his art and skills. Consequently, in the course of the development of society, the lexical structure of the language encounters unfamiliar words and terms related to the daily activities of mankind, its formation and development depended on the human mind and thinking. The profession of potter is closely related to clay and pottery, because the most important material for creating pottery is found on the surface of the earth.

Literature review

It should be noted that the study and research of the research topic based on the materials of other languages was partially completed by linguists. Russian linguist S.V. Rozhdestvenskaya in her dissertation entitled "Structural-semantic organization of pottery terminology in English and Russian" studied the structural and semantic features of pottery terms in English and Russian and identified the commonalities and differences of these types of terms in the above-mentioned terms. In addition, he reveals the root characteristics of pottery terms and the factors influencing the formation of this term group, analyzes and discusses the productivity of one or another terminological method in creating the researched terms, and clearly expresses his opinion [Rozhdestvenskaya. , 2009]. In addition, a number of Tajik linguists and scientists, for example: A. Tursunov [1963], Sh. Rustamov [1981], D. Khojaev [1988], M. Shukurov [1991], R. Gafforov [1991], D. Saymiddinov [2001], M. Kosimova [2007] have written separate articles and works on the classification of terms, the difference between a term and a commonly used word, the characteristics of the term's use, the place of the term in the lexical structure of the language.

Research methodology

It should be said that currently there is no single point of view about the ways and methods of forming words and terms. According to the linguist scientist J. Sager, there are two ways to organize terms: the use of words in the language structure, that is, the use of words in the language, and the creation of a new lexical unit [Sager, 1980, 71-80]. Terminologist V.M. Leychik emphasizes that the methods of forming the terms of a certain field of knowledge correspond to the methods of creating lexical unit's characteristic of this natural language [Leychik, 2007, 108]. In our opinion, different

views and opinions in this regard arise from the fact that each term has its own ways and methods of organization within each language. In the process of studying, analyzing and reviewing the collected materials, it became clear that the following terms and methods of terminology are widely used in the Tajik and English languages for creating terms related to the field of ceramics: sarifi or vandafzoi, that is, to create. term using prefixes and suffixes; spending; savings; lexical-semantic.

In this article, before paying attention to the structural analysis of pottery terms, simple terms are described first. Both languages have a large number of simple terms, most of which are nouns, that is, nouns represent a group of terms in the vocabulary of a comparative language in relation to other parts of speech: soil, clay, earthenware, pot, pot, g 'um, hearth [Peshchereva, 1959, 198]; clay, soil, pot, jug, etc. It consists of artificial terms constructed on the basis of the method of application or expansion of a large group of terms in the field of pottery in the Tajik and English languages. Thus, below, under the headings “formation of a term with a prefix” and “formation of a term with a suffix,” we will mention terms formed by two important word-forming units - a prefix and a suffix. Formation of a term with a preposition. In the Tajik language, the role of prepositions in organizing terminology is limited, but in English they make a significant contribution. Thus, the following English prepositions, from which pottery terms are formed, are presented as follows: re-: reformula - change the shape of enameled products, that is, change the shape; de-: degradation - the chemical process of separating water molecules from crystalline hydrates, especially clays and kaolins, when heated; non-: non-toxic preheat: preheat a ceramic dish or preheat the stove or oven; im-: unripe – raw, unripe; poly: polychrome, polychromatic – multi-colored, multi-colored, multi-colored, multi-colored; underfired - half-fired, semi-fired, unfired, glazed - paint or powder used in pottery before glazing; over-: overglaze - powder or ceramic coloring composition for coloring the surface of the glaze [T. N. G. VIDEL, 1971, 675].

Forming derivational suffixes. Compared to prefixes, the role of suffixes in the creation of terms in the field of ceramics of comparable languages is very large; below we will dwell on the level of their use and their place in terminology. Thus, in the process of analysis, repetition and comparison of the collected vocabularies and terms, the formation of the term was determined by the following numbers: -a: handle (part of an instrument, clay, mud or soil) of an instrument used during use: jug with handle, good command, solar team; stamp, calla, mola [Peshchereva, 1959, 139], sun, kunda, kabza, parra [Peshchereva, 1959, 168], jusha, etc. In most cases, instead of the equivalent suffix -a, the element -ak is used, which is often combined with adjectives and nouns, forming the term: pen, ear. The English equivalent of this suffix is the element -le: -le:mester - place, place: pitcher's handle, pitcher's handle or pitcher's handle, pitcher's handle; pot handle or pan handle; -y suffix: chini<Chinese suffix; ceramics<ceramics; pottery <pottery tools, pottery tools, pottery tools [Doro, 2021, 430].

It should be noted that the mentioned suffix is one of the most productive suffixes of the Tajik language, and the number of terms created through it is endless: lojuvardi, guppi, chashi, tagi, mori, sari, dukki, shorakki, kuvi., Chuli, Langari, Kalibaki, Qalandari, Nightingale, Islamic. The English equivalent of this suffix is the -ing element: abrasive, grinding; suffix -gar: potter [Daro Ch.1, 2021, 430]; potter [Daro, 2021, 440]; potter [Ayniy, 2013, 111]; potter [Gafurov, 2020, 633]; -on suffix: potters, craftsmen, artists; -chi: tanurist, trident [Peshchereva, 1959, 164], plate maker [Peshchereva, 1959, 207]; -gi: one, two, three, four, work; suffix -ak: blue, yellow, red [Peshchereva, 1959, 39]; Suffix -an: to cook, to put, to rub, to rub. The equivalent of the suffix -an in English is the prefix to, which repeats the initial form of the verb: to bake; adverb to lay down - grain: oven, stove, pot, lamp [Peshchereva, 1959, 74], statues, pot [Peshchereva, 1959, 155], candlestick, vase, bread. The suffix -don has no equivalent in English, the terms formed in Tajik are used in simple and complex forms in English: hearth, hearth, hearth, hearth, candlestick, base, rest, stand, support; foundation, flower bed [TNGWIDEL, 1971, 375]; - Gary: potter, potter, potter, bowl maker;

From the analysis and review of adverbs in the Tajik language, it became clear that they are divided into two subgroups: 1. Derivational suffixation and inflectional suffixation. It should be said that suffixes play a very important role in the creation of a term. In this context, we consider terminations necessary. Word-forming adverbs also play an important role in English, and we will

mention them below: -er suffix: potter - potter, potter; painter - polisher, polisher; blunger - equipment for cleaning with sand or sand; caliper gigger - ceramic wheel, ceramic circle, ceramic ring; damper - damper; suffix -lik: cooking, burning, burning, burning, belting, carving, facing, glazing, blackening, fixing; -ery suffix: pottery (pottery, tableware, ceramic, terracotta, stone, porcelain, porcelain) - ceramics; suffix -ium: barium [TNGWIDEL, 1971, 79] – barium; suffix -ous: amorphous [TNGWIDEL, 1971, 35] – amorphous, formless, dimensionless; - age suffix: compression - tension, pressure; -ory suffix: fireproof - fireproof, fireproof; suffix -ence: fluorescence [TNGWIDEL, 1971, 376] – emission, light; suffix -like: vitreous - vitreous, whiteness - whiteness; - or suffix: insulator - insulating material; accelerator - accelerator; -ed suffix: ripe - ripe, ripe; modified - product formation technology, processed; cooked - cooked; -oid suffix: colloid - colloid; - work suffix: clay - muddy, muddy, muddy; white blond - blond; finishing - finishing, finishing; -ment suffix: treatment - processing; Suffix: solubility - the ability to dissolve; -lash suffix: reduction.

Conclusion

To summarize, we can say that prefixes and suffixes are used to form a term. In both languages, the way to create terms using prefixes and suffixes is to add them to the root. In both comparative languages, prefixes and suffixes play a very important role in the formation of adjectives. Both parent adjectives and relative adjectives are formed using accusative cases and suffixes. The number of lexical terms in English is very limited: deflate - remove air from a soft paste, unmelted, inorganic - inorganic, lifeless; delamination is a type of glaze defect - a drop and its folds (folds), resulting from rubbing of the glaze or its thick layer or as a result of incomplete cleaning of the surface of the product [Pirov, 2019, 16]. In this article, before turning our attention to the structural analysis of pottery terms, the simple terms are first described. Both languages have a large number of simple terms, most of which are nouns, that is, nouns are a group of terms in the vocabulary of a comparative language in relation to other parts of speech: soil, clay, earthenware, pot, pot, g'um, hearth [Peschereva, 1959, 198]; clay, soil, pot, jug, etc. It is composed of artificial terms constructed on the basis of the method of applying or expanding a large group of terms in the field of pottery in Tajik and English. Thus, below, under the headings “formation of a term with a prefix” and “formation of a term with a suffix,” we will mention terms formed by two important word-forming units - a prefix and a suffix.

From the explanation of the term-forming elements of the English language, it became clear that the suffixes of this language have a very wide position in the formation of pottery terms.

List of used literature:

1. Каримов А. Таҳлили лексикӣ –грамматикии матнҳои тоҷикӣ қадим.–Душанбе, 1986. –127 с.
2. Шафоатов А. Н. Ташаккул ва таҳаввули истилоҳоти варзиш дар забони тоҷикӣ. – Душанбе, 2019 –191 с.
3. Нуров П. Г. Становление и развитие таджикской физической терминологии. Автореф...дисс.... –Душанбе, 1997. –27 с.
4. Якубов Ю. Раннесредневековые сельские поселения горного Согда (к проблеме становления феодализма). – Душанбе, «Дониш» 1988 –248 с.
5. Одинаев Б.Э. Исупова Р.А. Кулолгарӣ яке аз равандҳои ташаккули хунароҳои мардумӣ –Душанбе, 2019. –С. 3
6. Айнӣ С. – «Ёддоштҳо»–Душанбе, –Адиб, 1990. –С. 19
7. Гаффуоров Б. «Тоҷикон»(Таърихи қадимтарин, асрҳои миёна ва давраи нав) –Душанбе, –Наشريёти «Дониш», 2008. –С. 81
8. Саваониди Н.Ф. Картинный Археологический словарь(англо-русский) –Санкт – Петербург, 1995
9. Aliyeva M. O'zbek milliy gazlama dizaynerligi terminlarining semantik-grammatik tadqiqi: Filol.fan.bo'yicha falsafa dokt....diss. avtoref.-Farg'ona 2018. – В 16.
10. Айнӣ С. – «Ёддоштҳо» –Душанбе, –Адиб, 1990. – С. 197.

СЎЗ САНЪАТИ ХАЛҚАРО ЖУРНАЛИ

7 ЖИЛД, 2 СОН

МЕЖДУНАРОДНЫЙ ЖУРНАЛ ИСКУССТВО СЛОВА

ТОМ 7, НОМЕР 2

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF WORD ART

VOLUME 7, ISSUE 2

Контакт редакций журналов. www.tadqiqot.uz
ООО Tadqiqot город Ташкент,
улица Амира Темура пр.1, дом-2.
Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; E-mail: info@tadqiqot.uz
Тел: (+998-94) 404-0000

Editorial staff of the journals of www.tadqiqot.uz
Tadqiqot LLC The city of Tashkent,
Amir Temur Street pr.1, House 2.
Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; E-mail: info@tadqiqot.uz
Phone: (+998-94) 404-0000